

Simple example

Let $L := L^2((0, +\infty))$, $H := H^1((0, +\infty))$. Let I be the natural embedding of H into L . Let P be the orthogonal projection in H onto $H_0^1((0, +\infty))$.

[1]:

Let $J := I$. Then, J is injective. $A^{-1} - 1$ is Laplacian of Neumann boundary condition.

[2]:

Let $J := IP$. Then, J is not injective. $A^{-1} - 1$ is Laplacian of Dirichlet boundary condition.

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